

Attracting Investments in the Service Field and Using Them

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Abstract:

Attracting investments in various fields in the development of the country creates the basis for the prosperity of the economy of this country. However, just like there are two sides to a coin, there are some challenges in attracting investment. This article describes in detail the problems of attracting investments in the service sector.

Keywords: service sector, investment attraction, economic attractiveness, modernization, financial future.

Introduction

Currently, in the context of the globalization of the world economy, the development of the modern service sector is characterized by a high degree of specialization. At the moment, as a result of reforms aimed at modernization of modern sectors of the economy, technical and technological re-equipment, structural changes have been implemented in the service sector. As a result, the share of the service sector in the GDP is growing steadily. At the same time, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, "... first of all, the modernization of the service sector by moving to a qualitatively new level of quality service aimed at the rapid development of services to the population" is one of the directions. Studying the scientific-methodical and practical aspects of increasing the socio-economic efficiency of labor based on the effective use of the service sector is the effective solution of these tasks.

Indicators reflecting macroeconomic stability and economic growth rates in our country are a practical expression of the success of the reform strategy, deepening of economic reforms, and

achievements in the priority areas of our country's development. Today, in determining the current and prospective measures of socio-economic development of our country, it is necessary to comprehensively take into account the level of development of industries and sectors and their demand for personnel, and form economic development programs from the point of view of the impact of these processes. Therefore, effective use of services, which is an important factor of economic development, is an important factor of future strategic development.

One of the means of determining the effective use of personal services in the conditions of modernization of the economy of our republic is to determine the sources and reserves of labor efficiency improvement. Therefore, in order to adequately study the socio-economic nature of the labor productivity indicator, it is necessary to comprehensively analyze the interrelated labor indicators. In our opinion, achieving high work results based on the effective use of all material and labor resources is the main criterion for increasing work efficiency.

In world practice, it is important to develop targeted strategies to increase investment attractiveness in the development of the service sector in regions, to conduct active investment policy to ensure the sustainable development of the economy, and to conduct scientific and research activities aimed at ensuring the investment attractiveness of the investment environment. . In world practice, it is important to develop targeted strategies for increasing the investment attractiveness of regions, to conduct active investment policy to ensure the sustainable development of the economy, and to conduct scientific research work to ensure the implementation of investment attractiveness.

As the main condition for the formation of an innovative economy in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to accelerate investment activity, ensure stable and high growth rates, provide incentives and guarantees to local and foreign investors, and state regulation to ensure the effectiveness of these processes, including annual consistent measures have been taken to implement national and regional investment programs. In order to ensure the free entry of foreign investments into the economy of Uzbekistan and to form infrastructure based on international requirements, institutional changes, i.e. legal and regulatory documents, standards and requirements were developed, management structures were improved.

In recent years, we can see that the service sector is growing in the regions. Especially Fergana, Tashkent, Samarkand, Andijan, Tashkent. One of the important factors and directions of deepening the structural change and diversification of the economy, increasing the income and quality of life of the population in Uzbekistan is to increase the investment attractiveness of the regions. The essence of free economic zones for the country's economy are separate areas with clearly defined administrative boundaries and a separate legal system, established in order to attract local and foreign capital, promising technologies and management practices for the rapid socio-economic development of the territory. Free economic zones are an important part of the world economy, attracting foreign investments to many countries and showing their positive effects. EIH exists in different forms in different countries, and they are mainly united by one feature, that is, the preferential conditions introduced in these areas. Such a favorable environment is one of the effective methods of attracting foreign investment. EIHS are a key factor in today's integration and globalization processes. EIHS lead to the international exchange of capital by attracting foreign investors, while integration takes the process to a higher level through the flow of multinational companies.

In the context of the integration of the economy of Uzbekistan into the world economy, the implementation of export-oriented economic development policy in our country and the use of free economic zones in the production and export of exportable products, as well as high-tech production that replaces imports. The effective use of foreign trade policy experience of developed countries, especially China, Germany, France, Japan, South Korea, Singapore, where the global economy is rapidly developing, has a positive effect on the development of our national economy.

Accordingly, in the formation of the national economy, taking into account the specific features of the transition to a market economy, it is important to increase the country's foreign trade and export potential, in particular, to establish free economic relations through the liberalization of foreign economic activity. zones in the country. and the need to further improve the methods of their regulation. Effective use of the experience and methods of foreign countries in the establishment and effective management of free economic zones is one of the most important issues today. In particular, as stated in the third direction of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev "Development strategy for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", that is, "On further development and liberalization of the economy" : stability of the national economy, development of competitive products, export of products and materials. The composition of the services market is improving due to the development of new promising types of services - banking and finance, insurance, information and communication services and household services.

A sharp increase in providing families with sophisticated household appliances, computers and private vehicles has made it possible to expand the services provided to them.

Deepening the structural change and diversification of our country's economy, providing employment, increasing the income and quality of life of our people is considered to be one of the important factors and directions of rapid development of the service sector. One of the main directions of the reforms implemented in our republic is the development of small business and private entrepreneurship based on the service sector, creating new jobs with their help, organizing efficient and rational use of labor resources. As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: —How important is small business and private entrepreneurship specializing in the field of services, creating new jobs and increasing the income of the population, forming modern structures that ensure that the economy meets the requirements of the rapidly changing market? we need to understand deeply that it plays a role. Changes in the world economy require priority development of the service sector, like other sectors of the economy of Uzbekistan. Therefore, in the context of deepening reforms in our country, the development of the service sector is one of the priority tasks.

It remains urgent to improve the mechanisms for the development of the service sector based on the internal capabilities of our country. At the same time, it is worth noting the serious shortcomings in the development of this industry, in particular, the possibilities of providing services as a promising source of increasing employment and increasing the income of the population, as well as replenishing local budgets, are underutilized.

Conclusions and suggestions.

Creating favorable conditions for the rapid development of services and the service sector, increasing its share in the economy, increasing the number of people employed in the service sector and, on this basis, increasing the incomes of the population, as well as expanding the domestic consumer market with modern, high-quality products The existence of problems related to the filling of district services and the present circumstances show the relevance and importance of the selected topic in the current conditions. In general, the essence of the service is reflected in the following:

- service delivery is such an area that everyone encounters and that's why everyone considers himself an expert in this field;
- service requires an extremely individual approach;
- the high quality of the performed work leads to the high quality of service does not mean that it will come;
- most services have both tangible and intangible characteristics, they may be collectively referred to as the "service package";

- services are provided in close contact with the client and service by him consumed during the presentation process;
- effective management of an enterprise operating in the service sector in-depth knowledge of marketing and related operations, working with employees must have the ability;
- relations with the client's service organization during the service process can be imagined in the form of a sequence.

Acknowledging the above considerations, it should be noted that the service sector differs from production in many ways. These differences are explained by the fact that service depends on a high level of individuality, the speed of service, and the need to be in direct contact with the client during service. Demand adjustment schedules and protection mechanisms that can be applied in the manufacturing sector may not work in most cases in the service sector. In addition, the service industry requires relatively high labor productivity to meet the needs of customers. This, in turn, requires flexibility from employees involved in the service sector. In the last few years

Uzbekistan has undergone rapid economic transformation and is increasingly seen in the international community as a symbol of openness, renewal and determination to overcome various barriers to business and investment. For the effective implementation of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Investments and Investment Activities", 4 of the cooperation of state authorities, consisting of deputy heads of the Ministry of Investments and Foreign Trade, governorates, diplomatic missions abroad and commercial banks with investors a step-by-step mechanism has been successfully launched. This mechanism allows for a quick response to all investors' requests and the necessary control of the effectiveness of the measures provided for by the law. In this regard, with the support of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which ensures direct communication with investors operating in the Republic

It is important to emphasize the role of the Council of Foreign Investors. Liberalization of business activities is required to activate private investments. It is necessary to work diligently to identify and overcome obstacles that prevent the development of certain sectors, constant dialogue with business.

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